

AN EXPERIMENT: TEACHING SPEAKING SKILLS AT PG LEVEL THROUGH FLIPPED LEARNING APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Learning is a series of experiences to know, to learn and to implement. Benjamin Franklin was self-learned and a keen reader, he learned through experiences (Vega). This statement discusses the current teaching methodologies that are now actively practiced in engaging and encouraging learners to make learning more experiential and experimental. The prime objective of this study is to implement the latest teaching pedagogy for teaching speaking skills to the MCA students of Ganpat University and to identify the effects of flipped classroom model. The researcher has studied and observed that students do not give enough importance to English subject as compared to their technical subjects. Moreover, they pay attention to the first ten to twenty minutes in their Communication Skills Class. Therefore, they lack basic language skills such as LSRW skills. As a result, they are unable to fulfill the expectations of the interviewers in job interviews. For such techno driven generation, there is a need to develop a newly advanced pedagogy that is Flipped learning (FL). In FL approach, direct instruction passes from the classroom which is a group learning space to the home which is an individual/personal learning space. Hence, the classroom is converted into a vital and engaging learning environment where the teacher instructs students when they execute ideas/knowledge and engaged actively in learning the topic” (“Definition”). FL allows teachers to implement latest technologies in teaching that involve students actively in activities or discussion in the classroom. Here students become active learners rather than passive listeners.

Keywords: Flipped Learning, Flipped Classroom, Teaching Methodology, Learning, Technology

Introduction

In the 21st century, technology has provided wings to the educational world to fly beyond the classroom. Technology vista has widened its horizons in the field of higher education to make learning memorable, practical and experimental for the holistic development of students. This amalgamation of education and technology facilitates teachers to reach and teach the students more efficiently and in an interactive manner. At present, as teachers, it is the need of an hour to accept, appreciate and apply new learning methods such as a blend of

traditional and technological learning. Hence, flipped learning is a novel pedagogy in teaching of English language.

Flipped Learning

FL allows teachers to implement a mode/s in their classrooms to engage students in class time by allowing them to access the material before the class (“Definition”). FL speaks the language of millennial learners who are born and grew up in the age of the internet. These 21st century students prefer to learn the concepts by watching the videos at home and solving problems or discussing topics in the classroom (Bergmann and Sams 20). The Flipped Learning Network experts advised teachers to consolidate four pillars (F-L-I-P) into their teaching process (“Definition”).

These are described as follows:

1. Flexible environment: Teachers provide more opportunities to create flexible spaces wherein students can learn and do their tasks/activities/assignments by choosing their own time and place. Where learning is accessible beyond the classroom along with monitoring.
2. Learning Culture: The FL model promotes a student-centered approach, where class time is devoted to exploring concepts and generating more learning opportunities. Students are actively involved in problem solving activities/tasks/discussion to understand and learn the topic at depth (“Definition”).
3. Intentional Content: Teachers have to create learner – centered material to engage students before class, during class and after class actively. Teachers should know what and how to design content that can help students to understand and learn topics effectively.
4. Professional Educator: Teachers in FL model should have proper knowledge and training of scaffolding activities to facilitate their students’ learning needs. Here, the teacher’s role is more challenging than in the traditional classroom, they must constantly observe their students and give them feedback. “The teacher is not a sage on the stage but the guide by the side”, a facilitator, a mentor in FL approach (King 30).

Flipped Classroom (FC)

FC is termed as an inverted classroom where “the role of learning in the classroom and at home is inverted, homework is done in the classroom instead of at home with the support of the teacher” (Lage et al. 32). Flipped classrooms are flexible where learning and teaching happen beyond the classroom and students can learn on their own and at their own pace. (Bergmann and Sams 111; Khan 15-18). In a nutshell, flipped learning creates a conducive environment where learning takes place anywhere, at any time by anybody. FC gives more time to teachers for executing hands-on activities for the students that promotes collaboration and students-teacher interaction in class time (Lage et al. 37; Bergmann and Sams 25-26).

Relevance of the present study

It has been observed by the researcher that the attention span of the students in traditional lectures is hardly about ten to fifteen minutes (Khan 15). In technical institutes, Students lose their interest in communication skills lecture as it is considered a non-technical subject. It is also noted and observed at the time of placement interview that most of the candidates lack communication skills especially in Gujarat. One of the reasons is the lack of dynamic environment where learners can learn actively by practicing real life language. The flipped classroom becomes a dynamic learning place wherein students are involved actively in activities, discussion, clarifications and practice. They are exposed to learn language skills in FC.

It is the prime duty of a teacher to think about the best of the students. As many students take part in sports or cultural activities and go to the outstations due to, they miss some lectures and face difficulty at the time of exam. In flipped classrooms they can revise, learn, unlearn and relearn the subject by accessing subject material on their own and at their own pace (Bergmann and Sams 111).

Flipped Classroom V/S Traditional Classroom

In FC, students receive lecture notes / material in a form of video/ppt/documents related to the subject through Learning Management System (LMS), Google Classroom, WhatsApp, etc. well in advance. Therefore, students devote their class time in learning and practicing new concepts with the help of the teacher /classmates and sometimes work independently. FC promotes active learning theory where students become active participants and not just passive listeners. They think, analyze and evaluate the information presented to them in order to learn rather than memorizing it (King 31).

The researcher observed changes in computer assisted language learning that “students need the teacher physically present when they are stuck and seek his/her support. They don’t require the teacher to talk about the information which is already available in the books or internet and they can access on their own” (Bergmann and Sams 4-5).

In a traditional classroom, the teacher is the central figure in the classroom, main source of knowledge, where classroom time is divided between lecture notes and practice. Students receive information about the topic in the class and due to which they do not have enough time to complete the task/activity in class time and have to do it at home without the support of their teacher, or their peers. Students sit still and silent in their chairs and listen passively to the teacher for approximately fifty - sixty minutes. Because of this, the majority of the students get lost or bored at any given time, even if there is an expert teacher (Khan 113).

Statement of the Problem:

An Experiment: Teaching Speaking Skills at PG level Through Flipped Learning Approach.

Focus Questions

1. Does the use of flipped learning pedagogy will increase understanding of learners in learning a language?
2. Does flipped learning create conducive environment where learners can learn efficiently at anytime and anywhere through Google classroom?
3. Does flipped learning facilitate learners to develop speaking skills efficiently?

Conceptual Framework

The pedagogy for learning and teaching should be learner centered as learners come from different cultures, environments and with different learning capabilities. Diversity arises from the fact that students learn in different modalities and should be allowed to perform competency in the content through multiple ways. These ways are described by Gardener as modalities and multiple intelligences (Gardner 16). Flipped learning increases student–teacher interaction, it also permits students to pause and rewind their teacher through videos. Students can reuse videos for exam preparation to understand the subject effectively (Bergmann and Sams 23-24).

According to Alison King, “the role of a teacher in the traditional classroom is a teacher centered; where the teacher shares knowledge with the students; who just memorize the information to write in the exam, often without understanding it. This is known as the transmittal model, assuming that “the student's brain is like an empty container into which the teacher pours knowledge” where students are passive listeners rather than active ones (30).

The teacher’s role in FL is vital as it depends on the teacher to bring out the positive outcome of the learning. As quoted by Lewis, “technology is nothing without a teacher and a plan” (Lewis). So, it is the duty of the teacher to integrate teaching and technology. Teachers should create a “You Attitude” among the students and establish the faith in them that the teachers are interested in communication, collaboration and interaction for the students’ betterment.

An article published in The Print mentioned that the use of FC increases students’ placement, “AICTE affiliated technical institutes are ready to implement the FC model from 2019-20 academic sessions. Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) in various cities have already adopted FCM in some lectures. They believe that through flipped classrooms teachers can improve the learning standards of students and make them industry ready” (Sharma).

Methodology

The researcher has implemented flipped learning through Google Classroom for the students of Faculty of Computer Applications in Ganpat University. The main objective of this research is to enhance learners’ speaking skills using flipped learning approach. There were 48 PG students who have enhanced Speaking skills through flipped learning.

Figure 1: Google Classroom created for 48 MCA students.

Figure 2: Activity 1: Self-introduction, video shared through Playposit and YouTube

Figure 3: Activity 2: Know Your Buddy; Students' Videos were uploaded for observation

Two activities were carried out to test learners' language potential.

1. Self-introduction

2. Know your buddy

1.1 Step-1: Videos (TED Talk, NPTEL videos and YouTube Videos) related to self-introduction were uploaded well in advance and learners watched before the next class. A sample video on self-introduction was recorded by the researcher and shared with the students through Playposit by adding several questions in it.

1.2 Step-2: Learners recorded video of their own self introduction and uploaded in google classroom for teacher's observations. They made fewer mistakes after watching the sample videos and discussing with their classmates about several points which are included in self-introduction.

2.1 Step-1: Learners shared their views about the videos and discussed information about each other in a pair and then they introduced their buddies in front of the class.

2.2 Step-2: Learners introduced their buddies in an effective manner and recorded videos of this activity for their self-learning purpose.

Observations

- Learners made fewer mistakes when they introduced themselves and their buddies after watching the videos before class time.
- Learners were more confident and competent than they were before watching the sample video.
- Learners' gestures, postures and pronunciation of the words were up to the mark.
- Learners were positive about flipped learning methodology and shared their feedback as well.

In this small-scale research, the classroom time was devoted to working on activities discussion, assignments, research, quizzes, etc. students were imparted certain activities through Google classroom and WhatsApp on a regular basis and researchers surveyed the students through tools such as questionnaire, observation, classroom activities, quiz, etc.

There are many tools that can be used to make flipped learning more effective and interactive. Office 365 for Education is a free tool which can be assessed by entering a valid organizational email address. Edpuzzle and Playposit were used to make interactive videos by adding questions in it to engage students and increase their interest.

Data Collection and Data Analysis

Throughout the study, data were collected by the researcher using observation schedule, pre-test, post-test and questionnaire. The observation leads to implementation. The researcher has observed that students showed an active participation in the study and gradually their content knowledge was enhanced.

Figure 4: Students' responses regarding use of FCM

Two students who were engaged in another course on Microfocus and were not able to attend Communication Skills classes have commented that flipped learning has lessened their stress and made learning easy. They can play, pause and rewind videos to update lessons that they have missed. It is really a blessing that they performed well in this subject only because of FL approach.

Figure 5: FCM through google classroom

A survey was conducted through a questionnaire among 48 MCA students where questions related to flipped learning were asked. Wherein 100% of students replied that FCM gives them an opportunity to engage proactively in classroom activities and help them to learn the concepts easily by watching TED Talks, Vodcasts, and other educational videos (Fig. 4). They agreed that flipped classrooms give access to material to anybody, anytime, anywhere.

Moreover, 87% of students found that learning English in a flipped learning pedagogy through Google classroom made learning more experimental and experiential (Fig. 5). 94.3 % of students agreed that flipped classrooms promote self-learning (Fig. 6). Students said that they like

Name the activity that you enjoyed a lot while learning.

53 responses

Has FCM created a platform for self learning.

53 responses

Figure 6: Students enjoying learning through FCM

self-introduction activity most. They can speak with confidence about themselves. This activity is quite useful to them as most of the employers ask the question such as ‘Tell me something about yourself’ or ‘Introduce yourself’ and they will be able to answer it effectively due to this FL approach.

Major Finding of the Study

As per the above stated observations and result, the learners’ language skills were successfully enhanced through FL pedagogy. The major findings of the research work are mentioned below:

1. Flipping helps students, who are busy in other activities, to keep pace with their study.
2. It helps students of all abilities to excel.
3. FL approach makes content accessible at anytime, anywhere by anybody.
4. FL approach increases student-teacher interaction.
5. FL enhances understanding of the content and language skills of students.

Limitations and Further Scope of Research

The main challenge for this study is accessibility of the internet at rural places of Gujarat like North Gujarat, Panchamahals and tribal areas near Dahod. Another important factor is funding but educators can use free tools which are available on the internet.

In India minimal research has been done on flipped learning. It is a novel and untouched model which researchers can explore by incorporating educational technology in order to make learning more experimental and practical. During the CORONA pandemic students and teachers both have accepted learning through videos with open arms. Students learned virtually but they felt that virtual classrooms cannot take the place of physical classrooms. Therefore, flipped classroom or hybrid classroom is a preferable solution for teaching and learning English language to the 21st century students of India. This study was conducted on a small scale but it can be carried out by involving large samples and various technological tools to facilitate this research more efficiently.

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